

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ANATOMICAL AND ATYPICAL LIVER RESECTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898705>

Abstract

Liver surgery is historically one of the "youngest" areas in abdominal surgery, but at the same time it marks very rapid progress and continuous development, which continues even today.

Development of liver resection surgery has been linked to a parenchymal dissection techniques and reliable hemostasis and biliostasis,

The International Study Group of Liver Surgery (ISGLS) provides definitions and criteria for Evaluation of specific post-resection complications

Keywords: liver resections, complications after liver resections.

INTRODUCTION:

Prerequisites for the rapid development of liver resection surgery are the established anatomical knowledge of segmental hepatic anatomy, the improvement of techniques for parenchymal dissection and definitive hemo- and biliostasis, the improvement of hepatoprotection methods and means, the development of anesthesia and resuscitation care for operated patients.

OBJECTIVE:

Data collection and comparative analysis according to the technical characteristics of the surgical intervention with an emphasis on the type of resection – anatomical or atypical.

Determination of a possible prognostic role of the type of liver resection (anatomic or atypical) for the risk of occurrence, frequency and severity of postoperative specific complications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

For the period from January, 2007 - March, 2018 in Clinic of liver, biliary pancreatic and general surgery, Acibadem City Clinic Tokuda Hospital ,1021 interventions were performed on the liver:

Cases of intervention other than liver resection by definition were excluded ISGLS, "removal of part of the liver parenchyma due to involvement by a disease process or traumatic injury resulting in devitalization of the parenchyma".

Thus, the study did not find the cases of:

- hepatotomy;
- cystotomies and cyst resections, practically without removal of functioning or pathologically altered liver parenchyma;
- liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors. liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors;
- interruption of trunk branches of the hepatic artery and/or portal vein with the aim of hypoperfusion of a given area (segments, lobe);
- suture of the liver in trauma;

Thus, a total of 852 cases of liver resections were included in the series

Despite the improvement of the operative technique and the accumulated experience in centers with a high volume of activity, liver resection surgery is still accompanied by a mortality of the order of 0.24 - 9.7% and far more troublesome rates of complications - from 4.09% to 47.7%. (Table 1.) [1-10]

Table 1.

Post-resection mortality and morbidity of a number of leading hepatobiliary surgery centers

Author	Magazine	Year, month	country	Number cases	Disease, indication	Mortality, morbidity
Savage et al[1]	Ann Surg	December 1991	United States	300	Injuries, tumors	OMR = 19% (1962-1979) и 9.7% (1980-1988), OACR= 12.3%
Wu et al[2]	Zhonghua Waike Zazhi	05.2002	China	1762	Carcinomas, primary	OAMR=0.40%OACR=4.09%
Ishikawa et al[3]	Hepatogastroenterol	11-12.2002	Japan	139	hepatocellular carcinoma	OAMR=2.2%, OACR= 40.2%
Descottes et al[4]	Surg Endosc	January 2003	France	87	Tumors benign,	OAMR=0%, OACR= 5% (лапароскопски)
Dimick et al[5]	Arch Surg	01. 2003	USA	569	Tumors (benign, malignant)	OAMR=4.8%
Benzoni et al[6]	Hepatobiliary Pancreat Dis Int	11. 2006	Italy	287	hepatocellular carcinoma	OAMR= 4.5%, OACR= 47.7%
Benzoni et al[7]	Hepatogastroenterol	01.-02. 2007	Italy	134	hepatocellular carcinoma	OAMR= 7.4%, OACR= 47.7%
Mullen et al[8]	J Am Coll Surg	05.2007	USA	1059	Patients without cirrhosis	OACR=43%, OAMR 2.8%
McKay et al[9]	Ann Surg Oncol	05.2008	Canada	1107	Tumors	OAMR=6.0%, OACR= 46%
Feng et al[10]	World J Gastroenterol	12.2008	China	827	Tumors (benign	OAMR=0.24%OACR=13.5%
Tomuş et al[11]	Chirurgia (Bucur)	05.-06. 2009	Romania	50	Tumors (benign	OAMR=0% OACR= 18%
Cescon et al[12]	Ann Surg	June 2009	Italy	1500	Tumors (benign, malignant)	OAMR= 3%, OACR=22.5%
Huang et al[13]	Chin Med J (Engl)	10.2009	China	2008	Tumors (benign, malignant)	OAMR=0.55%OACR=14.4%
Mathur et al[14]	J Gastrointest Surg	08.2010	USA	3960	Tumors	OAMR=2.5% OACR=23.3%
Sato et al[15]	J Gastroenterol	10.2012	Japan	5270	hepatocellular carcinoma	OAMR=2.6%, OACR= 14.5%
Dan et al[16]	Chirurgia (Bucur)	11-12.2012	Romania	133	Tumors (benign, malignant)	OAMR=2.25%

OAMR= over-all mortality rate; OACR = over-all complication rate;

In 1982, an article titled "Surgical Anatomy and Anatomical Surgery of the Liver" was published in No. 6 of the World Journal of Surgery, authored by H. Bismuth.

This article presents and comments on all the knowledge of liver anatomy and physiology known up to that point and on this basis defines "typical" and

"atypical" liver resections. Additionally, Bismuth compares Couinaud's scheme on the one hand and Goldsmith and Woodburne's on the other, "smoothing out" the terminological differences between them. Last but not least, an important point in the publication is the comparison of Lortat-Jacob and T.T.Tung techniques for hemihepatectomy. (Table 2)

Table 2.

Anatomical and resection classification in liver surgery according to Couinaud, according to Goldsmith and Woodburn and according to the Brisbane Convention (Brisbane Congress of IHPBA, 2000)

Couinaud	Goldsmith and Woodburne	Brisbane	Резецирани сегменти
Right hepatectomy	Right hepatic lobectomy	Right hemihepatectomy	V, VI, VII, VIII
Right lobectomy*	Extended right hepatic lobectomy	Right trisectionectomy	IV,V,VI, VII, VIII**
Left hepatectomy	Left hepatic lobectomy	Left hemihepatectomy	II, III, IV **
Extended left hepatectomy*	Extended left lobectomy	Left trisectionectomy	II, III, IV, V, VIII **
Left lobectomy	Left lateral segmentectomy	Left lateral sectionectomy	II, III

RESULTS:

Some collectives comparing the early and late results after Anatomic liver resection and Atypical resection for metastases from colorectal carcinoma recommend Atypical liver resection for metastatic tumors in order to reduce the operative risk and the frequency of specific post-resection complications.

After analyzing the early postoperative results in the patients included in our study, we believe that there is no "one-size-fits-all" method of liver resection.

A guiding principle in our practice for interventions indicated by benign diseases has been "preserving the maximum volume of functionally fit liver parenchyma", and for malignant ones - "achieving R0". Both Anatomic Liver Resection and Atypical Liver Resection can be applied in either case.

When it comes to a benign process, only the early results are of interest – experiencing the resection without general or specific complications. Maximal preservation of functioning parenchyma, of course with adequate blood supply and biliary passage, with meticulous definitive hemostasis and biliostasis of the resection surface is justified.

The situation is more complicated in oncological cases. Here, in addition to the low risk of mortality and morbidity in the early postoperative period, the achievement of good long-term survival is equally important, i.e. reducing the risk of recurrence and/or metachronous metastases.[11-25]

DISCUSSION:

There is no universal method of liver resection.

Liver resection carries a higher risk of acute liver failure in the early postoperative period due to the loss of healthy, functioning liver parenchyma. But the majority of authors prove that the risks of occurrence of bilirubin and hemorrhage are greater in atypical resection due to compliance of the removed part of the segmental hepatic anatomy.

CONCLUSION:

A number of factors are important in determining the type of resection – Anatomic liver resection or Atypical and its volume:

-number, size, localization and type of the pathological lesion/lesions;

- volume of the healthy surrounding parenchyma, which will eventually be removed due to impaired blood supply and biliary drainage and/or due to "seeking radicality" in oncological cases (achievement of R0);

- presence and degree of compensatory hypertrophy of the residual parenchyma after any interventional procedure.

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